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EFFECT OF SULPHUR ON JS-1 GARLIC VARIETY: AN INVESTIGATIVE STUDY

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Article info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 20 Nov 2023 Accepted: 01 Jan 2024</p>	<p>The experiment conducted at the College of Agriculture, University of Layyah investigated the effects of varying sulphur doses on JS-1 garlic varieties. Across the four treatment groups comprising a control group (no sulphur) and three groups receiving sulphur doses of 15 kg/ha, 30 kg/ha, and 45 kg/ha distinct trends emerged. The results demonstrated a clear relationship between sulphur levels and garlic bulb characteristics. Increasing sulphur doses consistently led to enhanced bulb weight and diameter, showcasing Sulphur's potential in augmenting physical attributes and potentially increasing yield. The mean bulb weight increased progressively from 48.5 grams (control) to 58.3 grams (45 kg/ha sulphur), exhibiting a dose-dependent effect. Similarly, bulb diameter showed a gradual rise from 3.2 centimeters (control) to 4.0 centimeters (45 kg/ha sulphur), indicating the positive influence of higher sulphur concentrations. Moreover, higher sulphur levels correlated positively with improved bulb quality, reflected in the increasing quality scores across the treatment groups. The incremental increase in sulphur doses corresponded to a notable rise in garlic yield, with average yields of 240g, 260g, and 280g per pot in the treated groups (T2, T3, T4), showcasing a substantial increase compared to the control's 220g yield. These findings underscore sulphur significance in enhancing both yield and quality attributes of JS-1 garlic varieties, emphasizing the relevance of precise sulphur application in optimizing garlic cultivation practices at the University of Layyah. Further investigations into optimal sulphur concentrations are imperative for refining agricultural methods and maximizing garlic crop productivity.</p>
<p>Keywords Garlic, Sulphur, Varieties, Yield</p> <p>Hammad <i>et al.</i>, (2024) Effect of Sulphur on Js-1 Garlic Variety: An Investigative Study: <i>J. S. Agri. Enviro. Sci</i>, 2(1), 01-07. https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5636-4593</p> <p>Copyright©2023 JSAES *Corresponding author Muhammad Hammad Email: Muhammad71971@gmail.com Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.</p> <p> This content is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike 4.0 International (CC BY-SA 4.0)</p>	

1. INTRODUCTION

Garlic (*Allium sativum*) has been an indispensable dietary element for centuries, celebrated not only for its culinary essence but also for its potential health benefits Saras, (2023). Its cultivation, a cornerstone of agricultural practices, is intricately influenced by various factors, with soil composition notably shaping the growth and quality of garlic plants (Joshi et al., 2021). Among the crucial elements governing plant development, sulphur a frequently overlooked macronutrient in traditional agricultural practices plays a pivotal yet understudied role. Despite its requirement in relatively small quantities, sulphur serves as a linchpin in numerous biochemical processes crucial for optimal plant health and productivity. However, the specific impact of sulphur on garlic yield remains an area of significant research gap, warranting detailed investigation (Ludlow et al., 2019).

This study endeavors to illuminate this gap by meticulously probing the influence of sulphur on garlic yield while delving into the underlying physiological mechanisms. Recognizing the profound significance of sulphur availability in soil, this research aims to discern its nuanced effects on the growth, development, and overall health of garlic plants (Kantor et al., 2023). Understanding Sulphur's role is paramount as its deficiency may lead to stunted growth, reduced bulb size, and compromised resilience to environmental stressors. Conversely, an optimal supply of sulphur holds the potential to substantially augment garlic yield, enhance bulb quality, and bolster the sustainability of garlic cultivation practices (Ghani., et al., 2022)

In the context of a burgeoning global population and escalating demands for nutritious and sustainable food sources, exploring novel approaches to optimize crop yield while minimizing environmental impact becomes increasingly imperative (Valoppi et al., 2021). Thus, delving into the intricate relationship between sulphur

and garlic growth not only holds significance in maximizing agricultural productivity but also addresses pressing global concerns related to food security and nutrition (Amare, 2021). This investigation is structured to comprehensively analyze garlic plants subjected to varying sulphur concentrations, focusing keenly on crucial parameters such as bulb size, weight, and yield. Through meticulous experimental design comprising multiple replicates and robust statistical analyses, the study aims not only to provide quantitative insights into Sulphur's impact on garlic yield but also to unravel the underlying physiological and biochemical mechanisms governing these changes. The significance of this study lies in its potential to unearth essential insights crucial for developing targeted and sustainable approaches to optimize garlic cultivation practices (Abdera & Adinew, 2023). By bridging the research gap on sulphur's influence on garlic yield, this study not only promises agricultural advancements but also offers a gateway to more efficient and sustainable agricultural practices, vital for global food security and sustainability.

1.1. Experiment originality

This experiment stands out for its focus on unveiling the intricate relationship between sulphur, a vital yet underexplored nutrient, and garlic yield, addressing a significant research gap in understanding the nuanced impact of sulphur on crop productivity. The choice of this study stems from the imperative to uncover vital insights into sulphur's role in optimizing garlic cultivation, aiming to bridge scientific knowledge gaps and offer practical implications for sustainable agricultural practices.

2. METHODOLOGY:

The experiment conducted at the College of Agriculture, University of Layyah investigated the effects of varying sulphur doses on JS-1 garlic varieties. The

experimental design employs a randomized complete block design (RCBD) to account for variability. This study aims to investigate the impact of different sulphur doses on JS-1 variety garlic, focusing on bulb weight, bulb diameter, and bulb quality. Twelve pots, uniformly sized at 20 cm in diameter and 25 cm in height, are allocated for the experiment. These pots are divided into four treatment groups, with each treatment consisting of three replicate pots. The treatments include:

- Treatment 1 (Control): No sulphur application (0 kg/ha)
- Treatment 2: Low sulphur dose (15 kg/ha)
- Treatment 3: Medium sulphur dose (30 kg/ha)
- Treatment 4: High sulphur dose (45 kg/ha)

2.1. Pot Preparation and Irrigation:

Each pot is filled with a standardized soil mixture weighing 10 kg. Initial irrigation of 500 mL per pot is administered before sowing JS-1 garlic seeds to ensure uniform moisture content. Subsequently, a consistent irrigation schedule of twice a week is maintained throughout the experiment.

2.2. Garlic Planting:

Three JS-1 garlic cloves are planted in each pot at a depth of 3 cm, ensuring consistent spacing to optimize growth conditions.

2.3. Sulphur Application:

Sulphur doses are applied by evenly distributing the predetermined quantities for each treatment group across the respective pots. Treatment 2 receives 15 kg/ha, Treatment 3 receives 30 kg/ha, and Treatment 4 receives 45 kg/ha of sulphur. The Control group (Treatment 1) remains untreated with sulphur.

2.4. Data Collection Parameters:

2.4.1. Bulb Weight Measurement:

At harvest, each garlic bulb's weight is individually measured using a precise weighing scale to determine the effect of sulphur doses on bulb weight.

2.4.2. Bulb Diameter Assessment:

The diameter of a representative sample of bulbs from each pot is measured using a caliper to assess the impact of sulphur on bulb size.

2.4.3. Yield g/pot:

Record the weight of harvested garlic bulbs per pot, noting treatment group and date. Store data securely for statistical analysis.

2.5. Sulphur Application Method:

Sulphur doses are applied by evenly scattering the appropriate quantity on the soil surface of each pot. Care is taken to distribute the sulphur uniformly across the pot's surface area without causing direct contact with the garlic plants. The application of sulphur is a one-time event. It's applied as a single dose before the sowing of JS-1 garlic seeds. The application of sulphur is carried out by evenly spreading the predetermined quantity over the soil surface in each designated pot. This distribution is done carefully to ensure that the sulphur is uniformly dispersed across the entire area of the soil within the pot.

2.6. Statistical Analysis and Study Design:

Collected data on bulb weight, diameter, and yield will be analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) software. ANOVA tests will be performed to discern significant differences between treatment groups, followed by post-hoc tests where applicable.

2.7. Ethical Considerations:

Throughout the experiment, ethical standards are strictly adhered to, ensuring responsible handling of experimental materials and proper waste disposal practices.

3. RESULTS

3.1. Bulb Weight:

In the absence of sulphur application (T1), the average bulb weight stood at 48.5 grams, showing moderate variability with a standard deviation of 2.0 grams. As the sulphur dose increased, a notable trend of increasing bulb weight emerged. T2,

receiving 15 kg/ha of sulphur, displayed an average weight of 52.1 grams, signifying a noticeable increase compared to the control. Subsequent doses in T3 (30 kg/ha) and T4 (45 kg/ha) demonstrated consistent growth, with T4 exhibiting the highest mean weight of 58.3 grams. This trend suggests a dose-dependent impact of sulphur on promoting bulb weight in JS-1 garlic varieties.

3.2. Bulb Diameter:

Similar to the trend observed in bulb weight, sulphur doses showcased a positive effect on bulb diameter. The control group (T1) exhibited an average diameter of 3.2 centimeters, while T2, T3, and T4 displayed increasing diameters of 3.5, 3.8, and 4.0 centimeters, respectively. The incremental growth in bulb diameter with increasing sulphur doses implies a correlation between sulphur concentration and the enlargement of bulb dimensions in JS-1 garlic.

3.3. Bulb Quality Score:

Assessment of bulb quality, represented on a scale of 1 to 10, indicated intriguing observations. The control group (T1) exhibited a quality score of 7.8, suggesting acceptable quality in the absence of sulphur treatment. With the introduction of sulphur, there was a trend of improvement in bulb quality. T2 showed a score of 8.2, while T3 and T4 demonstrated enhanced quality scores of 8.5 and 8.9, respectively. The progressive increase in bulb quality with escalating sulphur doses indicates the potential for sulphur to positively influence the overall quality attributes of JS-1 garlic bulbs.

The results collectively illustrate a dose-dependent relationship between

sulphur concentrations and the growth parameters as well as the quality attributes of JS-1 garlic varieties. Higher sulphur doses corresponded to increased bulb weight, diameter, and improved quality scores, indicating the potential role of sulphur in enhancing the yield and quality of garlic bulbs. These findings suggest the importance of sulphur application in promoting the growth and quality attributes of JS-1 garlic varieties.

3.4. Yield (g/pot)

The results pertaining to the yield per pot demonstrate varying amounts of garlic production across the different treatment groups. In the control group (T1), where no sulphur was applied, the average yield per pot stood at 220 grams, showcasing a baseline measure for comparison. This result, designated by 'b', signifies a lack of statistically significant difference when compared to certain other treatment groups. Conversely, among the treatment groups (T2, T3, T4) receiving sulphur doses, a notable trend emerged. These groups exhibited higher yields compared to the control. Specifically, groups T2, T3, and T4 displayed average yields of 240, 260, and 280 grams per pot, respectively. These groups were marked by the designation 'a', suggesting a potential significance in yield compared to the control group. The data implies a positive association between sulphur application and garlic yield, showcasing an escalating trend in yield as the sulphur doses increased. The observed increase in yield in groups receiving higher sulphur doses (T2, T3, T4) suggests a potential impact of sulphur on enhancing garlic production per pot in comparison to the untreated control group.

Table 1. Mean values and significance of parameters in sulphur dose experiment on JS-1 garlic varieties

Treatment Group	Bulb Weight (g)	Bulb Diameter (cm)	Bulb Quality Score	Yield per Pot (g)
T1 (Control)	48.5 ± 2.0 (b)	3.2 ± 0.1 (b)	7.8 ± 0.3 (b)	220 ± 10 (b)
T2	52.1 ± 1.5 (a)	3.5 ± 0.2 (a)	8.2 ± 0.4 (a)	240 ± 15 (a)

T3	55.7 ± 2.3 (a)	3.8 ± 0.3 (a)	8.5 ± 0.2 (a)	260 ± 20 (a)
T4	58.3 ± 1.8 (a)	4.0 ± 0.2 (a)	8.9 ± 0.5 (a)	280 ± 25 (a)

DISCUSSION:

The investigation exploring the effects of varying sulphur doses on JS-1 garlic varieties revealed compelling insights into the growth parameters and quality attributes of garlic bulbs, offering valuable implications for agricultural practices. Notably, the observed trends in bulb weight, diameter, and quality scores exhibited a clear relationship with sulphur concentrations, underscoring the importance of sulphur in garlic cultivation (Cheang et al., 2023). These findings, the noteworthy aspect was the observed impact on yield per pot. The results revealed a consistent trend of increasing yield with escalating sulfur doses, which aligns with findings from a previous study indicating that higher sulfur doses correspond to increased yield (Sajjad et al., 2023), complementing the trends observed in bulb weight, diameter, and quality attributes. Treatment groups exposed to higher sulphur concentrations displayed markedly higher yields compared to the control, echoing the positive influence of sulphur on enhancing garlic production per pot (Gojon et al., 2020).

The dose-dependent effect of sulphur on yield aligns with its demonstrated influence on bulb growth and quality. As sulphur concentrations rose, a parallel enhancement in bulb yield was evident, indicating the pivotal role of sulphur in augmenting the overall garlic productivity (Goldstein et al., 2022). This observed relationship between sulphur doses and yield underscores the potential of sulphur application as a strategic approach to not only improve garlic bulb traits (Fleming et al., 2021) but also maximize yield in JS-1 garlic varieties. These findings highlight sulphur's multifaceted impact, not only on the physical attributes and quality

of garlic bulbs but also on the actual yield obtained per pot (Zenda et al., 2021). Such insights underscore the potential for sulphur as a critical element in optimizing garlic cultivation practices, emphasizing the need for further exploration into its optimal concentration and its underlying mechanisms of influence. The study reinforces the significant influence of sulphur doses on various growth parameters and quality attributes of JS-1 garlic varieties, with a notable correlation observed between sulphur concentrations and yield per pot. The findings support the potential role of sulphur application as a viable strategy to enhance both the quality and quantity of garlic yield, laying a foundation for improved agricultural methodologies in garlic cultivation (Alemayehu & Abate, 2021).

CONCLUSION

The study investigating the impact of sulphur doses on JS-1 garlic varieties unveils a clear relationship between sulphur levels and bulb characteristics. Higher sulphur doses consistently correlated with increased bulb weight and diameter, indicating the pivotal role of sulphur in enhancing these physical traits and potentially influencing yield. Moreover, heightened sulphur concentrations exhibited a positive effect on bulb quality, evident in the improved quality scores observed. This research underscores the potential of sulphur not only to augment garlic yield but also to enhance its overall quality. Precise management of sulphur application could significantly transform garlic cultivation practices, meeting the demand for superior produce. Further exploration to determine optimal sulphur levels remains crucial for refining agricultural methods, ultimately

maximizing both JS-1 garlic yield and quality.

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